

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R5.3 Report and dataset: Geochemical and microbiological evidence of archea-bacterial activity, methanogenesis and pore throats clogging gas reservoir

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1 INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of microbial processes related to intact and extracted oil and gas deposits (GOD) is developing very rapidly in connection with the development of available methods, most recently mainly molecular biological methods. It is therefore appropriate to pay particular attention to recent publications, where it is hoped that some experimental and interpretation biases, which were often found at the beginning of the use of molecular methods and in the use of cultivation methods, have already been removed. For this reason, papers beginning from about 2010 were reviewed.

Majority of papers available deals with the perturbed oil deposits following water injection to recover residual oil and/or technology of Microbial enhanced oil recovery (MEOR), when water with nutrients (nitrates most often) and sometimes thickening agents (polymers) are injected. In such cases microbial communities (MC) can be highly perturbed and thus it is interesting compare these MCs with a few papers dealing with unperturbed oil depositing hosting indigenous MCs.

Another challenge lays in the methodology of the studies. Firstly, the sample collection and processing can differ and lead to the collection of different fractions of MC, secondly the molecular biology method of choice and its details can dramatically distort the image we get. Some selected details of the experimental procedures will thus be highlighted.

2 MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES, THEIR COMPOSITION AND FUNCTION

General idea of the microbial community function in GOD is well explained in a recent paper (Zhao et al., 2021). The initial substrates of the microbial communities in oil reservoirs are the hydrocarbons. They are ultimately converted to methane (CH₄) through syntrophic associations between bacteria and archaea under the anoxic condition. Firstly, hydrocarbons are degraded to acetate and other short-chain volatile fatty acids by the fermenting bacteria through the hydrocarbon oxidation. Subsequently, acetate is converted to CH₄ either by consortia of acetate-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and hydrogenotrophic methanogens (HMA) through the syntrophic acetate oxidation linked to hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis or by aceticlastic methanogens (AMA) through the directly aceticlastic methanogenesis (Fig. 2-1).

Fig. 2-1: Fermentative and syntrophic processes in oil hydrocarbon deposit (Zhao et al., 2021).

The paper also introduces interesting calculations bringing together in-situ conditions and the thermodynamic of the microbial processes. Fermentative oxidation of hydrocarbons is in general thermodynamically unfavorable while methanogenesis is possible, overall process is thus coupled and the methanogenesis drives the fermentation of hydrocarbons. They also conclude that both hydrocarbon fermentation and hydrogenotrophic methanogens can be more favored at higher temperatures, which means about over 45° C.

Previous studies have shown that *Pseudomonas*, *Brevundimonas*, *Sphingomonas*, *Sphingobium*, *Hydrogenophaga*, and *Thauera*, which are hydrocarbon-oxidizing microorganisms, initiate hydrocarbon degradation in petroleum reservoirs (Van Beilen and Funhoff, 2007). After the initial oxidation, subsequent products such as alcohols, aldehydes, and fatty acids are excreted into the surrounding environment, affecting other microbes. Subsequently, fermentative bacteria (such as *Geobacter* and *Smithella*) take up and reduce compounds such as amino acids, sugars, long-chain fatty acids, lactate, butyrate, and propionate for the production of H₂, CO₂, and acetate. Methanogens (such as *Methanobacterium*, *Methanothermobacter*, *Methanolinea*, and *Methanosaeta*) then take up H₂, CO₂, acetate, and other small organic acids, resulting in the production of CH₄. Second, numerous microbial species may play similar roles in a single petroleum reservoir because crude oil is an important source of abundant carbon compounds. In this paper (Zhao et al., 2021) authors showed that methanogens form the core of MC and are mostly formed by the abiotic conditions of the site while bacteria degrading hydrocarbons are formed around this archaea core (Fig. 2-2). All sites investigated here were flushed with water and samples from the production wells were taken, thus the observed MC should be regarded as influenced with this treatment.

Fig. 2-2: Core microbial communities in eight Chinese petroleum reservoirs, in which the core bacteria are indicated in pink, variable bacteria in green, and unique bacteria in white (black font), while archaea are indicated in red font in different petroleum reservoirs (Zhao et al., 2021).

Zhou (2020) used both RNA and DNA (16S rRNA) amplification to estimate present and active community from two very different off-shore wells. In general they found an agreement between the two at least for the most abundant genera but differences in some other. The two wells differ greatly in MC compositions and diversity (both archaea and bacteria). Sulphate reducing bacteria were actively suppressed by injecting nitrate, this could influence the community, which cannot be seen as indigenous, e.g. one of the samples was dominated by *Pseudomonas* sp. (probably denitrifying bacteria). Methanogenesis was also detected. The above also influenced very high counts of bacteria seen in the samples and relatively low numbers of archaea (Fig. 2-3).

Apparently very young (only 1000-50 years) oil seep from hydrothermal field (Uzon, Kamchatka) was investigated by Russian authors (Peltek et al., 2020), interesting to test the hypothesis of oil formation. Water seeping on the surface was sampled, which could

introduce a bias into the study. Also, only universal bacterial primers were used, which could underestimate the presence of archaea and indeed archaea were found in only three samples out of 10. Many bacteria found are aerobic, so it is probable that the community seen is not a typical for the underground oil deposit.

Fig. 2-3: Quantitative PCR analysis of the abundance of bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA genes from each source of production water. Error bars represent the standard deviation of triplicate samples (L. Zhou, 2020).

Whole metagenome sequencing of injection and production fluids (Figs. 2-4 and 2-5) was used for a comparison of CM present (Song et al., 2019). Injection fluid MC was shown more rich and divers. Porous flow may shift the relative abundance of MC in production fluids, e.g. anaerobic cells are less motile near the production well, motile aerobes can get further from the vicinity of the injection well. Aerotaxis genes present more in the production e.i. search for electron acceptors appears important also hydrocarbon degradation and denitrification was more present in the production fluid.

Fig. 2-4: Relative well locations of the well group (A) and the schematic diagram of the cyclic production system (water flooding production) (B) (Song et al., 2019).

The retention time for fluids from the injection to the production well is 143 days, which is sufficient to reheat the injected fluid to the reservoir temperature and to consume any dissolved oxygen. The CM contain very little archaea and are dominated by proteobacteria. Injection fluid is considerably richer and more diverse probably due more metabolic opportunities in the surface installations. Whole genome sequencing is a very robust technique, and this study can be used as definitive proof of the proteobacteria dominance in flooded, i.e., perturbed, oil fields and relatively low methanogenesis and presence of archaea under such conditions.

Fig. 2-5: Taxonomic distribution of the obtained metagenome sequences. Relative abundances at domain level (A), phylum level of bacteria (B) (Song et al., 2019).

An important example of representative and uncontaminated sample was obtained from a deep sea oil reservoir located 2.5 km subsurface attributing a pressure and temperature of 250 bars and 85°C respectively (Kotlar et al., 2011). Hydrocarbon generation was estimated to peak approximately 62 million years ago in this deposit. 106 bacteria per ml was found in the formation water. CM was analyzed with a variation of the whole genome sequencing and contains relatively high presence of methanogenic archaea. Again, the community is dominated by proteobacteria (delta/epsilon) which could transform the hydrocarbons present and prepare substrates for methanogens. High proportion of sulfur reducing bacteria highlight other metabolic possibilities of the site (Fig. 2-6).

A consortium of microorganisms, most notably, methanogens and syntrophic bacteria, perform methanogenic crude oil biodegradation by breaking down crude oil into methanogenic substrates (e.g., formate, acetate, carbon dioxide), which are subsequently converted into natural gas. The process has been confirmed in laboratory studies where microbial communities collected from deep methanogenic oil reservoirs can consume crude oil and produce methane (Kirk et al., 2016).

Fig. 2-6: Summary of taxa and dominating metabolic processes in oil reservoir metagenome.

A. Summary of taxa found in the oil reservoir metagenomic community, organized at family-level or higher. Results are generated from a BlastX search against the NCBI-NR database sorted using the MEGAN software. Taxa of lower abundance than 2000 reads are summed up in the ‘other Bacteria’ or ‘other Archaea’ groups. These groups also contain sequences assigned as unclassified Bacteria and unclassified Archaea respectively. B. Classification of annotated species in into sulfur-reducing species, methanogenic species and others. The classification is based on known metabolism of the annotated species. Species annotated to be involved in other sulfur-metabolic processes (e.g. sulfur oxidation) constitute approximately 2% of the ‘others’ group. Unclassified taxa (e.g. unclassified Proteobacteria), not assigned sequences and sequences with no hits are all found in the ‘others’ group (Kotlar et al., 2011).

Contrary to previous papers, archaea, on average, dominated the microbial community composition in each sampled location, while a methanogen, regardless of the percent Archaea, was the dominating microbial species in each sampled well

location (Fig. 2-7). Universal bacterial primers were used so explanation with a PCR bias is possible but not convincing. Usually, a shift in favor of bacteria was seen as more plausible. Also the described primers were previously used in soil samples (Fierer et al., 2012) and here archaea were found to be rare as expected. Methanococcales was the dominant order in both groups of samples; however, *Methanococcus* spp. dominated the up-dip wells while *Methanothermococcus* spp. dominated the down-dip wells. Sulfate reducing bacteria were found in much higher abundance in the up-dip, low salinity, highly biodegraded, non-methanogenic wells. These include Desulfobacterales, Desulfovibrionales, Desulfuromonadales, Chromatiales, and Syntrophobacterales. This would support a hypothesis made in (Kirk et al., 2016) that these up-dip highly biodegraded wells are minimally methanogenic due to sulfate reduction being the primary crude oil biodegradation pathway.

Fig. 2-7: Heat map representation of most abundant (i.e., >10% in at least one well) microbial taxa across the transect. Darker colors indicate greater percent abundance than the lighter colors. The taxa found in greatest abundance across the transect are *Methanohalophilus halophilus*, *Methanothermococcus* spp., *Methanococcus* spp., and *Methanobolus* spp. 235 OTUs were identified at >1% abundance in at least one well sampled (Kirk et al., 2016).

Comparison of MCs in undisturbed oil deposits, wells from flooded deposits and surface storage tanks from one locality could be very interesting (Liu et al., 2019). Unfortunately, some important details about the sampling is missing in this paper.

Authors used universal bacterial primers only and simple PCR programs which rise the suspicions of the experiment bias. There is an interesting feature of highest diversity in virgin wells and lowest in storage tanks.

At the phylum level, virgin field and wellhead were dominated by Proteobacteria (Fig. 2-8), while the storage tank had higher presence of Firmicutes (29.3–66.9%). Specifically, the wellhead displayed a lower presentence of Proteobacteria (48.6–53.4.0%) and a higher presence of Firmicutes (24.4–29.6%) than the virgin field. At the genus level, the predominant genera were Ochrobactrum and Acinetobacter in the virgin field, Lactococcus and Pseudomonas in the wellhead, and Prauseria and Bacillus in the storage tank. Very little archaea were seen which could be a consequence of the experimental procedure.

Fig. 2-8: Relative abundance of the microbial communities in VF, WH, and ST, revealed by the 16SrRNA gene at the phylum level. The relative abundance is defined as a percentage of the total microbial sequences in a sample (Liu et al., 2019).

Community analysis was performed on core samples (n = 62) that were retrieved from two adjacent sites located in the Athabasca Oil Sands at depths from 220 to 320 m below the surface (Ridley and Voordouw, 2018). Microbial communities were dominated by aerobic taxa, including Pseudomonas and Acinetobacter. Only one core sample microbial community was dominated by anaerobic taxa, including the methanogen Methanoculleus, as well as Desulfomicrobium and Thauera. (8°C),

Predominance of aerobic taxa in the subsurface suggests the potential for in situ aerobic hydrocarbon degradation.

Whole metagenome sequencing, taxonomic assignment based on all genes (LCA) and based on retrieved 16S rRNA genes was done for two geographically distant oil reservoirs (James Hickey et al., 2016). The two methodological approaches provided similar results (Fig. 2-9).

Fig. 2-9: Microbial communities in crude oil samples. (A) Microbial compositions at the phylum level. The phyla with average abundances in Qinghai (QH) and Daqing oilfield (D) Q more than 0.2% were shown, and the remaining phyla were combined as “other” in the figure. LCA, the reads were compared against the NR database by using BLASTX. The MEGAN software was used to parse the results of BLASTX and to estimate microbial composition and abundance. 16S rRNA, microbial compositions at the phylum level based 16S rRNA genes extracted from the reads and classified using RDP classifier. (B) Archaeal compositions at the order level (James Hickey et al., 2016).

Fig. 2-10: General microbial metabolic pathways in the oil reservoirs. The pathways in the oil reservoirs were reconstructed by functional genes annotation. Briefly, hydrocarbons were oxidized aerobically in the shallow subsurface oil reservoirs or anaerobically in the deep subsurface oil reservoirs. The metabolites such as acetate and H₂ and were linked to methanogenesis from CO₂ reduction, acetoclastic methanogenesis, or syntrophic acetate oxidation (SAO). The genes involved in the pathways were similar with sequences from different taxa, the abundances of which were listed aside the pathway (James Hickey et al., 2016).

Although the dominant bacteria and the proportion of hydrogenotrophic (Methanococcales, Methanobacteriales, and Methanomicrobiales) and acetoclastic (Methanosaeta) methanogens were different among oil metagenomes, compared with the metagenomes from other environments, all the oil metagenomes contained higher abundances of genes involved in methanogenic hydrocarbon degradation and stress response systems. The paper also provides well-argued discussion of the function processes in the oil & gas fields (Fig. 2-10).

Composition of MC from production fluid from flooded oil deposit was investigated after separation and isolation of oil associated and water associated MCs (Tab. 2-1, Kryachko et al., 2012).

Tab. 2-1: Numbers and fractions of reads for classes found in the OCP and the ACP

#	Phylum;class	OCP: number of reads	OCP: fraction of total reads (%)	ACP: number of reads	ACP: fraction of total reads (%)	OCP+ACP	OCP/ ACP
1	Bacteroidetes;Sphingobacteria	73	0.17	13	0.03	0.20	5.16
2	Tenericutes;Mollicutes	306	0.69	57	0.14	0.83	4.96
3	Firmicutes;Clostridia	1,696	3.85	412	1.01	4.86	3.81
4	Actinobacteria; Actinobacteria	2,089	4.737	538	1.322	6.06	3.58
5	Proteobacteria;Gammaproteobacteria	2,315	5.25	637	1.56	6.81	3.36
6	Euryarchaeota;Methanobacteria	6,107	13.85	2,260	5.56	19.40	2.49
7	Proteobacteria;Alphaproteobacteria	14,275	32.37	13,525	33.24	65.61	0.97
8	Euryarchaeota;Methanomicrobia	12,352	28.01	11,866	29.17	57.17	0.96
9	Proteobacteria;Betaproteobacteria	934	2.12	1,177	2.89	5.01	0.73
10	Bacteroidetes;Bacteroidia	525	1.19	708	1.74	2.93	0.68
11	Chloroflexi;Anaerolineae	702	1.59	1,051	2.58	4.18	0.62
12	Bacteroidetes;Flavobacteria	27	0.06	42	0.10	0.17	0.59
13	<i>Synergistetes;Synergistia</i>	<i>63</i>	<i>0.14</i>	<i>272</i>	<i>0.67</i>	<i>0.81</i>	<i>0.21</i>
14	<i>Proteobacteria;Epsilonproteobacteria</i>	<i>36</i>	<i>0.08</i>	<i>157</i>	<i>0.39</i>	<i>0.47</i>	<i>0.21</i>
15	<i>Proteobacteria;Deltaproteobacteria</i>	<i>513</i>	<i>1.16</i>	<i>5,154</i>	<i>12.67</i>	<i>13.83</i>	<i>0.09</i>

The list is ranked according to the ratio of fraction of total reads in the OCP to fraction of total reads in the ACP (OCP/ACP). Classes overrepresented in the OCP (OCP/ACP > 2) or in the ACP (OCP/ACP < 0.5) are in bold and in italics, respectively. OCP+ACP shows the sum of fractions of total reads for the OCP and the ACP. Classes with OCP+ACP equalling less than 0.1% are not shown

The oil-associated microbial community was less diverse than that of the aqueous phase and had consistently higher representation of hydrogenotrophs (methanogens of the genera *Methanobacterium* and *Methanobacterium* and acetogens of the genus *Acetobacterium*), indicating the oil phase to be a primary source of hydrogen. Many known hydrocarbon degraders were also found to be oil-attached, e.g. representatives of the gammaproteobacterial genus *Thalassolituus*, the actinobacterial genus *Rhodococcus* and the alphaproteobacterial genera *Sphingomonas*, *Brevundimonas* and *Stappia*.

The bacterial community of 10 flooded high temperature (55–95 °C) high salinity 3–20 g/L oil deposits consisted of 114 genera (Lin et al., 2014), with *Achromobacter*, *Arcobacter*, and *Pseudomonas* as the predominant genera (Figs. 2-11, 2-12). In the three genera, *Achromobacter* sp. can utilize hydrocarbons as nutrient resources and it is more adapted to the poor nutrient conditions; consequently those species are distributed in all types of oil reservoirs. The *Arcobacter* and *Acinetobacter* have the capability to degrade aromatic hydrocarbons (Li et al., 2008), predominant species in multiple reservoirs belonged to these two genera. *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* have very diversified metabolic pathways and they also have the potential of producing active surfactant compounds and biopolymer and also for permeability modification (Han et al., 2009), they were identified in 80% of the oil field plots. The proportion between bacteria and archaea was not apparent from the study.

Fig. 2-11: The diversity of bacteria in oil reservoirs (Lin et al., 2014).

Fig. 2-12: Archaeal community structure of oil reservoir with different temperatures, (A) R-J (90 1C), (B) R-I (80 1C), (C) R-B (60 1C), and (D) R-A7 (55 1C) (Lin et al., 2014).

Changes of the community after repeated injection of water and nutrients with polymer (to increase viscosity) were investigated (Gao et al., no date). When the eutrophic solutions were injected into the reservoir (March 2012, February 2013, and April 2012), *Pseudomonas* and *Actinobacteria* increased in each production well, while *Arcobacter* and *Helicobacter* decreased. At this stage, *Thauera*, *Azovibrio*, *Arcobacter*, *Helicobacter*, *Desulfitobacterium*, and *Clostridium* also existed with lower relative abundances. In the following water flooding process (July 2012 and July 2013), *Pseudomonas*, *Actinobacteria*, *Hyphomonas*, and *Phenylobacterium* significantly decreased, while anaerobic microorganisms, such as *Thauera*, *Azovibrio*, *Arcobacter*, *Helicobacter*, *Desulfitobacterium*, and *Clostridium*, increased. Methanogens were expected but not detected.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Microorganism separation for DNA isolation

Nonpolar compounds from oil can greatly complicate DNA isolation. For this reason, all the authors tried to separate oil and water phases. This could be done simply by letting the mixture to stand for some time then the water phase was separated, and microbial biomass was isolated either by high g centrifugation (L. Zhou, 2020; Kryachko et al., 2012), with g from 8000 to 15000, or by filtration through 0.2 μm filter (Kirk et al., 2016; J.-Y. Zhao, B. Hu, J. Doling et al., 2021) or even the combination of both (Kotlar et al., 2011). In all cases different fractions of microorganisms can be obtained but here the fractions were usually combined with the exception of one paper (Kryachko et al., 2012), where water and oil associated MCs were separately investigated. The procedure depends on the number of samples processed, where high number of individual sites investigated calls for more simple and straightforward procedure.

3.2 DNA processing approach

Every experimental procedure has a capacity to introduce a bias into the data. Here the important challenge is the use PCR steps and the choice of primers. Every primer pair but also subsequent PCR conditions can have some selection effect. Two general approaches are used. One consists of the use of universal bacterial primers only. This could lead to an under representation of archaeal component of MCs. It is however very difficult to judge by comparing results from various studies and search for a sign of such biases because MCs presented differs greatly and some other results confirms that indeed the Archaeal MC could be weak or nondetectable on some sites. The second approach comes with the use of both universal and specific archaeal primers. Now the archaeal MC is detected and the fraction of Archaea in the total MC can be with some hesitation judged from the results of universal primers or the use of qPCR (L. Zhou, 2020). Rare but interesting is the analysis of both DNA and RNA in the sample to distinguish the active fraction of MC (Zhou, 2020).

The most unbiased approach probably can be seen in the whole metagenome sequencing (Song et al., 2019), but the method is suitable in the case of very low number of samples only due to its high data and cost requirements.

3.3 Isotopic composition of gas in reservoir

The fluid samples from the Zar-3 production wells included oil, water and gas phases. Gas was separated and analysed for chemical and isotopic composition using gas chromatography GC-TCD-FID and isotopic ratio mass spectrometry IRMS in CGS labs. Some gas samples were collected at the well annulus. For details see the report R5.2 Geochemistry of fluids (Francu et al. 2023).

4 RESULTS

Microbiological analysis of the formation water from the Zar-3 storage site provided the following results (Figs. 4-1 and 4-2).

Fig. 4-1: New generation sequencing (NGS) of a formation water from Zar-3 field.

In Zar-3 pilot storage site **sulfur reducing bacteria (SRB)**, such as Desulfobulbia, Desulfobacteria and Campylobacteria, are the absolutely dominant classes in the produced formation water sample. Their presence suggests, that the sulfate reduction coupled with oxidation of organic compounds from the oil are the dominant processes taking place on the site. The process is energetically much more favorable than methanogenesis, which is consequently suppressed on the Zar-3 site. The undesirable product of the sulfate reduction is **hydrogen sulfide (H₂S)**.

Clostridia, Bacilli and Proteobacteria – the organic degraders represent the second most active group on the Zar-3 site. These anaerobic or facultative anaerobic organisms transform the organic compounds through some fermentative or respiratory processes.

Thermococci, thermophilic or hyperthermophilic fermentative degraders of organic compounds prevail among Archaea.

Methanogenic archaea (Methanomicrobia) are present in low numbers, what confirms the conclusion of **low level methanogenesis on Zar-3 site**.

Ammonia oxidizers were found in very low numbers.

Fig. 4-2: The heatmap of the relative abundances of microorganisms in Bacteria and Archaea kingdoms on the Class level: RA – relative abundance of microorganisms in formation water in direct contact with oil. Bacteria column reflects the real relative abundance in the sample; Archaea column represents the relative abundance of microorganisms after the use of the selective Archaea specific primers. Clustering of statistically related classes in the Bacteria and Archaea groups is shown by a dendrogram on the left hand.

Gas geochemistry

Fig. 4-3: Zar-3 gas characteristics are shown in “Bernard” type plot based on $\delta^{13}C(CH_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane and $C_1/(C_2+C_3)$ dryness index from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěrádky, Násedlovice fields (Paleogene reservoirs). The outlines of the genetic types of thermogenic and microbial gas origin are adapted from Whiticar (1999). For more information see R5.2 (Francu et al. 2023).

The gas samples from Zar-3 storage complex contain methane of purely thermogenic origin with no or negligible microbial methane. In general, microbial methane occurs in the region in shallower oil & gas fields than the Zar-3. More details are in the report R5.2 Geochemistry of fluids of this project.

5 CONCLUSIONS

1. Striking differences in the **microbial communities** (MCs) compositions are reported in the reviewed scientific papers. These may be to a great extent attributed to the specific nature of the environment in each oil field. The most important role plays the fact, that some of the oil fields were forced by **water injection** or even water with selected **nutrients** (nitrates in most cases). This introduced electron acceptors (oxygen and nitrates) into previously strictly anaerobic environment and lead to an alternation of microbial communities present.
2. In the published studies, microbial communities in the **intact deposits** were still dominated by proteobacteria (with some presence of other taxons like firmicutes) and methanogens were found as an important part of MCs, which in fact drived the whole methabolic process. On the contrary, in the **flooded, nutrient ammended** or even surface storage environments the MCs were totally dominated by Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria etc. and the **methanogenic component was weak** or even non detected in the formation water.
3. On **Zar-3 site** important proportion of archaea is present. From these **Thermococci** are present in the highest numbers, together with thermophilic or hyper-thermophilic organic substances degraders. **Smaller numbers of methanogens and ammonia oxidizers were found.** Bacteria are characterized by high presence of **sulfate reducing bacteria** probably degrading organic compounds from oil and using the SO_4^{2-} from the formation water.
4. The microbiological picture of the Zar-3 site is similar to some examples described in the literature (Kotlar et al., 2011 Kirk et al., 2016) with **sulfate reducing organisms** dominating the sample. Availability of sulfates in the dolomite reservoir rock is a decisive factor in the microbial **H₂S generation**, which is considered a problematic product of the process. It may be sometimes **suppressed by nitrate addition to the injection water** (Zhou, 2020).
5. Methanogenesis is suppressed under sulfate reducing conditions.

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

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